

ABOUT THE HISTORY OF AZERBAIJAN-BULGARIA TRANSLATION

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Abstract

The article examines the development path, main stages and mutual cultural and intellectual influences of the Azerbaijani-Bulgarian translation history. The aim of the research is to determine how cultural transfers, literary ties and diplomatic relations were formed through translation activities between the two peoples. These ties were enriched by the translation of works by such classics as Nizami, Samad Vurghun, Huseyn Javid, and also introduced the creativity of Bulgarian writers to the Azerbaijani reader. Various stages are considered; the most important examples and translator personalities in the fields of literary, scientific-popular, folklore and official-documentary translation are analyzed. The terminological, ideological and sociocultural difficulties encountered in the translation process are shown, using both a linguistic and a cultural study approach. The results show that translation is one of the main vectors of cultural dialogue between two peoples and stimulates literary-canonical exchange by deepening mutual understanding.

Keywords: Azerbaijani-Bulgarian translation history, translation, cultural transfer, literary exchange, Soviet period, terminology, translator personalities.

Translation activities based on ancient historical roots are also important and meaningful in modern social reality. Cooperation between nations, the exchange of national and cultural values, as well as the social and spiritual development of mankind are impossible without translation. Translation activity dates back to before our era. In the course of history, there are such truths that have always been reflected in the language of people, preserving their value. The rich heritage of peoples living far from each other, such as fairy tales, bayats, legends and epics, has been brought to our modern times precisely through translation. Translation activities have gone through a centuries-old development process and had a significant impact on the interaction of languages, as well as on the formation of literary and intercultural relations.

Translation activities provide residents of one country with the opportunity to get acquainted with the lifestyle, way of life, history, literature, scientific traditions and cultural values of other nations. If language is an existing natural system of society, then in the process of speech and communication, in the process of transmitting information, the activity of the language and the translator simultaneously recreates information through two different linguistic sign systems. Translation is an important tool that forms the basis for rapprochement, friendship, mutual development and cooperation between peoples. Without the art of translation, we would not be able to use the achievements of science and culture not only of the West, but also of the East, of which we are a part, and cultural and historical development cannot be imagined without translations. As the Azerbaijani poet and translator Vagif Bayatli Oder said: "For me, translation is love. If you do not love the work you are translating, the native language you are translating, then something strange will arise that cannot be loved" [1, p.25].

The language, culture, and literature of each nation are strong and powerful if that nation has excellent translated literature. This nation has a strong culture and literature because it translates the spiritual and cul-

tural achievements of other nations into its own language and benefits from it. The importance of translation activities and translators in the international activities of states is indisputable. When communicating with native speakers of different languages, both domestically and abroad, translators always play the role of intermediaries. The culture of all peoples is a unity of national and international elements, the grammatical structure of the language should be studied in the context of everyday life, lifestyle, customs, psychology, religion and the history of the people.

In recent years, the development of linguoculturology in Azerbaijani linguistics has also aroused interest. Linguoculturology has emerged as an independent scientific field in linguistics. This science considers its main task to be the study of the mutual influence of language and culture, as well as the relationship between language and national mentality. The subject of linguoculturology is the linguistic landscape of the world, and linguoculturology is an actively developing field of linguistics. Although linguoculturology is a relatively new field of linguistics, it has historically been associated with a close relationship between language and culture. The art of translation plays an important role in teaching any language. Speaking about translation as a cultural trend, they focus mainly on two points: the process of creating a translated text and its result. Recently, theorists have put forward three main models for studying the translation process: situational, transformational, and semantic. The famous Russian translation theorist V.N. Komissarov, paying special attention to these models in his book *Modern Translation Studies*, emphasizes that the situational model studies the translation process through linguistic concepts based on the relationship between language and reality [9, p. 210].

Bulgaria is one of the countries in Eastern Europe that has established the closest cultural ties with Azerbaijan. The relations between the peoples of Azerbaijan and Bulgaria have an ancient history, including in the field of translation. Since the 50s of the last century, cultural ties between Azerbaijan and Bulgaria have been developing, which have become regular, and

translations of Azerbaijani literature into Bulgarian are of great importance for the recognition of our spiritual wealth in our country. Outstanding Azerbaijani poets and writers have created wonderful works dedicated to Bulgaria and the Bulgarian people, and Bulgarian writers have written and continue to write about Azerbaijan. Assimilation of the national literature of a people in a different environment is a very broad concept, and the first of them is scientific and literary perception, and the second is translation. Bulgarian literary works translated in Azerbaijan are presented to readers in book publications, as well as in newspapers and magazines. One of the main directions of literary relations between Azerbaijan and Bulgaria is the widespread introduction of Azerbaijani themes into Bulgarian literature and Bulgarian themes into Azerbaijani literature. The development of literary ties between the two countries is encouraging. The poems of the great representative of Azerbaijani literature Nizami Ganjavi were translated into Bulgarian and published in the 19th century. Nizami Ganjavi is one of the greatest personalities who has left an indelible mark on world literature. The poet's works, which have become the cultural heritage of our people, reflect the historical past and traditions not only of Azerbaijan, but also of the peoples of the world. The poet's poem "Leyli and Majnun" was translated into Bulgarian and published by Professor Ivan Ivanov, the author of a number of famous works. The author notes that "Leyli and Majnun" is the second masterpiece of Azerbaijani literature after "Dede Gorgud's Book". "Leyli and Majnun" played an important role in the development of not only Oriental literature, but also world literature in general. Samad Vurghun, who visited Bulgaria twice, also wrote poems describing the history and culture of the Bulgarian people. Samad Vurghun's poem "On Bulgarian Soil", written in 1934, and the poem "The Chair of Death", dedicated to the heroic son of the Bulgarian people, Georgy Dimitrov, made a significant contribution to the development of Azerbaijani-Bulgarian literary ties and at the same time paved the way for the recognition of other Azerbaijani writers in Bulgaria. This work, with its lively dialogues and clearly written scenes, gives the impression of a documentary about the recent past. Perhaps the poem is not relevant today as an ideology (communism), but the determination to fight for a certain cause, the dignity of not bowing to the enemy is always relevant. The ballad "The Poet's Last Night", written by Bulgarian poetess L. Daskalova, is dedicated to the outstanding representative of Azerbaijani literature Samad Vurgun. The work expresses the grief caused by the death of Samad Vurgun in an emotional and poetic way, thus reflecting the author's love for Azerbaijan and its culture. Prominent Azerbaijani writers and poets Mehdi Huseyn, Mirza Ibrahimov, Huseyn Abbaszade, poets Suleiman Rustam, Nabi Khazri, Nariman Hasanzade have become famous in Bulgaria since the beginning of the century. The works of the classics of Bulgarian literature Ivan Vazov, Hristo Botev, Emilian Stanev and others have also been translated into Azerbaijani.

Along with all of the above, it should be emphasized that, considering the history of translation of the

Bulgarian people, Bulgaria is one of the leading countries in the field of translation and translation theory.

Vlakhov Sergey Ivanov is a Bulgarian translator, translation theorist, lexicologist and lexicographer, lawyer by training.

Sider Florin is one of the founders of Bulgarian translation studies and the founder of the Bulgarian Translators' Union. He was a first-class translator.

An extensive study of the realities in linguistics was conducted by Bulgarian linguists Sergey Vlakhov and Sider Florin. Realities are the names of objects, concepts, or events belonging to a people, nation, or country. Realities have no equivalents in other languages. S.V. Vlakhov and S. Florin consider as realities "groups of words denoting certain concepts belonging to another people". Realities are transferred to other languages through translation. There are a number of difficulties in translating these words. Sergey Vlakhov and Sider Florin, together and separately, devoted significant work to the theory of translation and lexicography. Their joint book "The Untranslatable in Translation" is an exceptionally in-depth study classifying scientifically untranslatable elements of language, that is, units that have no equivalents, and is an excellent textbook for any translator [10, p. 10]. In 1947, the first holistic theory of literary translation, Fundamentals of the Art of Translation, was created in Bulgaria, translated and authored by Lubomir Ognyanov. Lubomir Ognyanov has beautifully translated twelve plays by W. Shakespeare, and these translations attest to his knowledge of the specific subtleties of his stage speech. A person who is able to express his thoughts freely and flawlessly in his native language is always one step ahead of others. However, the greatest happiness is to speak the language of other peoples, exchange ideas with them, and enrich your inner world and worldview.

Anna Lilova is a researcher, translation theorist, and professor at Sofia University. Bulgarian translation theorist A. Lilova, emphasizing the significant influence of sociology on translation studies, notes that it is impossible to fully understand a translation without a deep understanding of its social nature, essence and functions. She emphasizes that translation does not exist outside of society, and a sociological approach is necessary for its scientific definition [11].

The works of prominent representatives of Bulgarian literature – Hristo Botev, Lamar, Tonichin Antinov, Nikolai Vajarov, Liana Daskalova, Elizaveta Bagryan, Ivan Kolarov, Kruma Grigorova, Jordan Milevin, Lyudmila Stoyanova and others – are well known to the literary community and readers of Azerbaijan and are read with pleasure in our country. Among the poems about Azerbaijan are the works of Bulgarian writers Tochev "Hello, Azerbaijan", "Baku Nights", K. Krainov "Decorate the World!", L. Elenkov "Ancient Baku", L. Daskalova "Azerbaijani Poem", the ballad "The Poet's Last Night", J. Mileva "In Mardakand", "Gay gel".

The "selected works" of Azerbaijani writer, playwright, and public figure Jalil Mammadkulizadeh – "Mailbox" and "Molla Fazleli" – were first translated from Azerbaijani into Bulgarian by Sofia Shigayeva-Mitreska, students of the Faculty of Turkology of Sofia

State University Aysun Yumer “Kishmish Game”, Alper Emurlov “Master Zeinal”, Chiydem Aliosmanova “The Bearded Child” and “Dallek”, Lilia Yordanova “Restlessness”, Janet Nikolova “Maybe they are back”. Artistic translation contributes to the dynamic development of the language; Each successfully translated work stimulates the emergence of new artistic patterns in the native language. When translating any short story, poem, novel, or drama from a foreign language into our language, there is both an explicit and a hidden contradiction between the two languages. The higher the resistance force, the more natural and free the sound of the translated text in the native language is considered. Various lexical and grammatical changes made during translation do not affect the accuracy of the translation. In general, when translating articles and essays, as well as journalistic materials, one should preserve the emotional diversity created by various stylistic means and expressions. The process of borrowing words from another language is a generally accepted rule in the world, no one objects to it. At a certain stage in history, borrowed words flooded into the language like a torrent, and it is very difficult, and perhaps impossible, to prevent this. If we look at how loan words are conveyed in the target language, we will see that loan words make up the majority in most languages. Most of the words in the vocabulary of the Azerbaijani language are words of national origin, and as a result of certain contacts with other peoples, many borrowed words have entered our language, sometimes it is very difficult to distinguish some words from others. “There are two sides to the development of language: one is the development of language under the influence of the external environment, and the other is the internal development of language. External and internal factors are closely related to each other in the development of any language. The role of linguistic relations in the development of languages and the study of their changes create significant difficulties in this area” [8, p.218].

As in Azerbaijani, there are many borrowings in the Bulgarian language, and the question of when and how intensively borrowings penetrated into the Bulgarian language raises questions. The appearance of borrowings directly affects the purity of the language. Bulgarian linguists come to the conclusion that borrowings that have no equivalents in the Bulgarian language are of Turkic origin, and some of the borrowings penetrated into the Bulgarian language precisely because they had no equivalents. The Bulgarian translation of J. Mammadkulizade’s short story “Mailbox” often contains borrowings. Borrowings are expressions that have passed from one language to another and entered its lexicon. According to the translators, each translator should find answers to three main questions before starting work. what does the author want to say, what meaning does he put into it and how does he express it? These words are often used to express new concepts, technologies, and cultural influences. Let us consider examples: *ханьт* (*хан*), *юфка* (*уиха*), *сандьче* (*sandiq*), *кутия* (*qutu*), *дамга* (*datğa*), *адаш* (*adaş*), *конак* (*kon-yak*) are words of Turkic origin included in the lexical fund of the Bulgarian language. The accuracy of the

word choice in translation is of great importance. As you know, in addition to the original and logical meaning of a word, there are also various shades of meaning that are sometimes not reflected in dictionaries. Or not all dictionaries reflect all these shades of meaning, and the meaning of a word that a translator needs appears only in the text.

The novel “Absheron” by Azerbaijani writer, playwright and critic Mehdi Huseyn was translated into Bulgarian in 1949. A few years later, the first book of the writer’s novel “Sugar” was translated into Bulgarian under the name “Awakening” and published by the Bulgarian publishing house “Narodnaya Kultura”. The translator was the writer Dimitri. Mehdi Huseyn created an artistic image of Baku oil workers in the work “Absheron”.

The novel juxtaposes two opposite poles of human nature. The novel “Absheron”, which tells about the life of Baku oil workers, is in a certain sense a continuation of the novels “Black Stones” and “Underground Rivers flow into the Sea”, which deserve attention for their bold intervention in social, moral and ethical problems. The writer reflects with his inherent skill the struggle of nature with natural forces, the characters of the novel, on the one hand, take an irreconcilable position with nature, on the other – with social evil, and the work celebrates the relationships of people, which are an integral part of their social life. One of the positive aspects of the novel is that patriotism is vividly represented here, vividly, in the work and activities of people. The Daskalovs, who came to Azerbaijan in 1972, translated poet Nabi Khazri’s poems “The Testing Cauldron”, “The Sea” and “Love” into Bulgarian and published them in the Bulgarian-Soviet Friendship magazine.

Momchil Shopov and Janet Nikolova translated and published the works “Maral” and “Sheida” for the 135th anniversary of Huseyn Javid, who created unique examples of philosophical lyrics in our national poetry.

Huseyn Javid’s play “Sheida” describes the fate of people who sold their souls to the devil for material goods. The writer shows that people who consider materialism to be the main incentive in life, those who treat innocent people unfairly and cruelly, those who destroy humanity with their cruelty, crimes and betrayal, invariably suffer disasters. The work condemns betrayal, crimes, cruelty and oppression.

The famous poet Siyavush Mammadzade translated the works of Bulgarian writers into Azerbaijani.

Bulgarian popular literary portal “meridian 27.com” and the official Facebook page of the World League of Bulgarian Writers began publishing poems by the young and talented Azerbaijani poetess Leyla Aliyeva, “Why did I suddenly get angry?” and “You are an Unquenchable Flame”, translated into Bulgarian, within the framework of the project “Azerbaijani Literature in the International Virtual World”. Leyla Aliyeva creates and presents her works in the style of *petik* in Russian. Her poetry is translated not only into our native language, but also into various languages of the world. The translation of Leyla Aliyeva’s works into world languages made it possible to bring samples of Azerbaijani literature to a global audience of readers with different psychological mindset and cultural

codes. The work of the Austrian historian, scientist and writer Erich Feigl "The Land of Lights on the Silk Road – The History of Azerbaijan" was translated into Bulgarian and published by Todor Enev publishing house. In the book "The Land of Lights on the Silk Road – The History of Azerbaijan", the author writes that one of the main sections of the work focuses on the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. The author comprehensively examines the historical roots and chronology of the Armenian-Azerbaijani, Nagorno-Karabakh conflict, and also reasonably conveys to the reader the fair position of Azerbaijan. Based on historical sources, this section of the book describes in detail the history of Karabakh from ancient times to the Khanate period, the mass resettlement of Armenians to the region, the roots of the baseless idea of "Greater Armenia", the massacre committed by Armenian nationalists with the support of terrorist organizations, and the acts of genocide committed against the Azerbaijani people. Much attention is also paid to the issue of the occupation of Azerbaijani lands at various stages of the 20th century. At the same time, the book provides detailed chronological information on the course of the Armenian-Azerbaijani Nagorno-Karabakh conflict from the 1990s to 2006. In this book, Feigl clearly proves to the reader that an in-depth study of the history of a people and a country is of great importance for a more complete understanding of the essence of the problems existing in the modern era. Erich Feigl's work provides readers with extensive and complete information about Azerbaijan's historical and cultural ties with neighboring nations. This book, rich in colorful illustrations, detailed explanations and comments, is an important scientific source reflecting the European perspective on the past, present and future of Azerbaijan. The translator of the book, Todor Enev, stressed that the publication confirms the resettlement of Armenians to the Caucasus with historical facts and presents the crimes committed by them to the reader in full. He noted that if Armenian politicians abandon their phantasmagoria, falsifications of history and extend a helping hand to their Azerbaijani colleagues, they will be able to live as friendly neighbors without war and victims.

According to poet, writer, translator Ramiz Rovshan: "In my opinion, translation is a bit like a sur-

gical operation. Translating a work of art from one language to another is like transplanting a body part from one living organism to another. The work of a surgeon can be considered successful only when this part of the body can live in another organism. This also applies to works translated into other languages" [1, p. 25].

The history of Azerbaijani-Bulgarian translation relations has played an important role in the formation of cultural, literary and scientific ties between our peoples. Thanks to their translation activities, both peoples got acquainted with the rich literature, historical heritage, customs and traditions, scientific achievements of each other, and a solid foundation for mutual understanding and cooperation was created. These relations influenced the development of not only artistic creativity, but also scientific and social thought, bringing our peoples closer together. The history of the Azerbaijani-Bulgarian translation is also of particular importance in terms of preserving and transmitting universal values to future generations.

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